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M-Learning as a convenient support to the learning process in computer science

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ABSTRACT

Many studies undertaken in the field of education have revealed that m-learning is emerging more and more as an effective learning method with the use of smartphones. Always turned on and easily transported, smartphones can be used anywhere, at any given time and in any context. Considering the potential of m-learning, we seek to understand this novelty as a support in the learning process, especially in computer science education. To reach this end, we asked a group of students their opinion in the form of a survey, in order to know the most beneficial aspects of a mobile application in education. The outcome of this survey helped us to develop a mobile application from which students could access course news, work timing, frequently asked questions and results. After using this application, a second survey highlights students' interest. We thus show that, especially for courses such as programming courses, m-learning plays a full role as it offers accessibility to valuable information which comes in a continuous flow to support the learning process and as it offers an environment where interaction with the learning tool can be adapted and adjusted to the learner's style and needs.

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INTRODUCTION

For years, we have been following educational paradigms that promote formal and well-structured learning. In these paradigms, the teaching work is reserved for designated people who oversee delivering knowledge to learners. Currently, the focus in higher education has moved from that concept of teaching to one that develops the idea of learning. In many universities, a paradigm shift has put the focus on student learning. Rather than focussing on the skills, capacities and best practices of teaching, universities are now analysing student performance [1]. The use of mobile devices is one of the main aspects of this educational change. These devices have led to a new learning style known as mobile learning or m-learning, offering dynamic, connected, and collaborative methods of finding and exchanging information. [2], Along with various developments in the field of information and communication technology, the smartphone has become a common tool, giving opportunities to learn on the go. By invoking the concept “m-learning”, one thinks spontaneously about the possibility of learning without being in a fixed or determined place [3]. It should be stated that m-learning is not a mere function of mobile devices within an e-learning spectrum, but a useful part of an increasingly rich and complex learning process [4].

To be able to fully benefit from m-learning, the understanding of its novelty is a must. This requires moving beyond superficial definition and examining the capabilities of mobile devices and the context in which the learner accesses the learning content [5]. It is a re-thinking of learning originating from the student’s perspective.

Understood in this way, m-learning is an extension of e-learning. Generally, e-learning refers to learning and teaching supported by electronic tools of all kinds. In e-learning, there is always a gap in time between the learning process and its application. Although electronic tools are used in m-learning, the learning and its application form a whole because they happen simultaneously. The goal is to give necessary information at the exact time. M-learning offers learners the opportunity to quickly check relevant and necessary information for the task to be accomplished.

Recognizing these differences, our efforts focus on conceiving m-learning as a useful support to the learning activity. Thus, the remaining sections of this paper continue as follows: The next section highlights a new perspective on m-learning. Then we present m-learning in a context of learning computer science. Before the conclusion, we describe our test results which confirm our argument.

1 M-LEARNING FROM A NEW PERSPECTIVE

1.1 Viewing M-learning as a Support

In the context of academic training, the number of supports to acquire knowledge is constantly increasing. Various new ways of learning are being invented with new learning tools. Today, many young students are using smartphones to access a variety of content in various fields. It may be relevant to offer them ways to support their learning with an application available right in their hands at anytime and for as long as they choose [6].

However, the use of smartphones comes with challenges. Considering the advantages and limitations of mobile devices, the design of a fully-structured mobile learning course encounters several setbacks. Because of the screen size of a mobile phone, m-learning content is often designed in small chunks, easy to digest on the go. This content is not a fully-developed course, just pieces of information necessary for the learning process [7].

In this context, m-learning should be thought of as a complementary way to augment or enhance all types of learning [8]. It is a performance support that focusses on applying and bringing to life the knowledge gained through formal instruction [7].

In providing performance support, mobile learning allows learners the freedom and flexibility to learn, not only when and where they choose, but also in view of satisfying specific needs. Learners can pull information up in the moment as required to support their work tasks. It is a learner-centric solution that puts the learner in control of his learning requirements, instilling greater confidence and offering an educational experience that is just enough and just in time [2].

Instead of relying on the knowledge that you acquired long ago and hoping you memorised everything then, mobile learning as support gives you the resources you need to deal with daily academic problems. Conceived as a support, m-learning offers students information they need to move on with their assignments and to instantly answer questions about the tasks they are performing [7].

1.2 Mobility Principle

In our society, the mobile device has become a permanent companion of the young and the adult, the rich and the poor. As one of many common and affordable electronic devices, the majority of people possess a smartphone [9]. Being in a constantly evolving environment where information is constantly changing, using smartphones in an m-learning environment becomes important to keep track of all updates and to support your learning while on the move.

The principle of mobility endows m-learning with a specific role. It empowers students to move freely within, beyond and between multiple environments and between topics and disciplinary contents and contexts. It means that learning is not confined to formal educational contexts; it is extended within opportunities such as home and work, and is offered not as a one-way exchange from lecturer to students, but as two-way learning within participating communities [1]. Mobility allows m-learning to become an environment where the learning content is available when it is needed most [10].

1.3 Personalisation Principle

It is a fact that the usage of m-learning is growing, and is affecting people's lives by introducing innovation and methods. The reason for this growth is not only for comfort of use and mobility, but also improvements in interaction and functionality in different contexts. It is crucial that the learner's contextual information is very useful for adapting his learning flow. The added value that m-learning can provide is therefore necessarily through personalisation. This idea of personalisation refers to the possibility for the learner to display the learning content according to his choices. This allows the display of specific content to increase performance. It offers an adaptive m-learning environment where the learner is exposed to learning materials that fit his individual learning styles.

In this sense, with the possibility of personalisation, m-learning becomes a useful support in a truly mobile learning context. It includes personal mood, interests, and willingness to learn, taking into account the current location and other people's influence [11]. If conceived as a support, m-learning must be an environment where interaction with the learning tool can be adapted and adjusted to the learner's style and need.

As m-learning is increasingly becoming a popular mode of learning, the learner can use mobile terminals to access a variety of information without constraints or

limitations[12], all the more so if he has the option of personalising his learning process according to his availability and the circumstances surrounding him [5].

2 THE CONTEXT OF COMPUTER SCIENCE LEARNING

In talking about m-learning, computer science learning is not an exception. There is ongoing research where researchers are working on tools to support the learning of programming on mobile phones [13]. Solutions have been developed that would enable students to learn programming using mobile phones. The biggest challenge for all the attempts is how to turn mobile phones into functional programming environments, even though they haven't been designed with programming functionalities.

However, it is still difficult to think of having an exclusive m-learning formula for that domain. It is obvious that for teaching a programming course, the computer is still an unavoidable tool. In this context, the use of mobile applications can therefore only be considered as a complementary tool to support the learning activity. So, what can such applications bring to us? Which services can be relevant? What are the factors that may affect the effective use of mobile devices in a programming lecture?

It is true that mobile phones support strong features like computers and can now offer incredible learning experiences. But in the context of learning computer science, input and output methods are important. Keypad and screens are very essential for programming learners and if it is generally agreed that using multi-monitor workstation significantly increases the productivity [14][15], the smartphone's screen and keypad are not convenient for many learning activities.

Besides, computer science courses involve particular constraints which do not exist in other courses. One of many characteristics of computer science courses is that they comprise many learning activities for which smartphones cannot be used. For example, the mastery of configuration of the integrated development environment (IDE) in the programming task, practical application of programming methodology, effective organisation of teamwork by using version control system (VCS), to name but a few, are integral components of learning. Unfortunately, they are difficult to envision other than by using a workstation.

Considering these limitations, in a programming class, m-learning finds its place as a collaborative tool that offers updates about the work, notifications, comments, deadlines, new assignments and so on. The important point to mention about m-learning in this case is the emphasis on the support and the collaborative nature of mobile learning applications [16].

3 METHODOLOGY

The goal of our study is to examine how mobile devices can be used as a support tool to complement other learning approaches, especially in computer science.

3.1 The Use of Smartphones in Student's Everyday Life

One question guided our interest: How do students informally use their smartphones for educational purposes? In order to have a clear preliminary orientation, we sought the opinion of a group of students, in the form of a survey, about the most beneficial aspects of a mobile application in an educational field.

In this exercise, 135 students in an undergrad programming course from Laval University responded to various general questions in an online survey. It appears that it is very natural for students to collaborate and use their phones to obtain instant information. As shown in Table 1, within an academic setting, most students exchange information with their classmates using smartphones and they use their phones to

access online information about a topic. Moreover, a large majority consult their correspondence (e-mails, academic notifications) on mobile devices, and use these mobile devices to keep track of their daily work and update their address books. Also, the majority consults the course website on their mobile devices relatively often. However, while many believe that mobile devices promote exchange, discussion and collaboration, it was noticed that few use it to participate in forums linked to the course. But almost half of them use it for social media.

Table 1. Students' answers on how they use their smartphones in everyday life.

Use in everyday life	Percentage of responses
Exchanging information with others	81
Online search for information on a topic	77
Keeping well-informed of current events related to personal activities	65
Keeping the calendar and address book up to date	58
Reading articles from newsletters or magazines	53
Sharing opinion reactions on a subject	34
Other	13

During this survey, the majority affirmed that promoting the use of mobile devices in education is a good idea and can provide many advantages. Indeed, the respondents would be very interested in a mobile application that allows them to access information related to the courses they are taking or related to their academic progress. They are also in favour of a mobile application to access academic news, updates and specific links about course materials, but their views diverge on the use of a mobile application to access administrative information. The summary of their answers is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Interest in a mobile application allowing access to information-related courses.

Information-related courses	Percentage of responses
News, updates, specific links to information	61
Information about academic progress	61
Administrative information	52
Information from student associations	21
Other	8

In addition, respondents were able to make several proposals such as being able to access their results, to configure their own alerts, for example, the schedule of the courses in which they are enrolled, dates for deadlines. This first survey allowed us to consider the development of a prototype application enabling us to confirm the orientations on the services to be taken into consideration as well as their degree of relevance.

3.2 Prototype

For this purpose, we conceived and developed a mobile application tool viewing m-learning as support, meaning a tool that offers instantly valuable information necessary to move on with the learning task at hand. The design of this mobile application tool

presents one interface for the student. In this interface, if the student is enrolled in the course, he is directly connected to the course website through the mobile application. The course news tab is a place where the professor can describe the work to be done, display information about the code solutions that provide support or guidance to carry out the work, or even post solutions for similar problems. The frequently asked questions tab is about technical problems encountered when students are working with the programming code. It is a place where they can post a piece of code and the output from it to illustrate their question. It offers room for testing their work as they move on. Mainly, this learning tool served as a support to keep the student informed about course progress. The interface has four layouts designed using Extensible Markup Language (XML). These layouts are: the news tab, answers to frequently asked questions (FAQs), a time-management aid, and the results tab. All these tabs are presented using nested doll patterns displayed on the top of the screen.

3.3 Results and Discussion

We tried out the application with a group of students enrolled in an undergrad C++ programming course; 42 students participated in the exercise. After the experiment, we invited them to respond to a short survey to get their feedback and appreciation of the application. Responses allowed trends to be identified. The analysis is intended to verify the current and future impact of the use of a mobile application in computer education. The results trace a picture of what can frequently be done with the smartphone.

What is interesting is that more than 78% affirm the importance of the mobile application in their studies. Most students express the need for a mobile application offering easy access to course news and student questions about tests and various assignments as well as the professor's answers and comments on these questions. They also wanted the mobile application to display tests recalls and various work deadlines, or course results. Even though the initiatives of a mobile learning application at Laval University remain recent, respondents could see the benefits. A large majority of respondents found access to news, work deadlines and frequently asked questions very important or important. But only 60% found access to work results very important or important. The details of responses are presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Students' answers on the importance in their studies of the "services" offered by each tab of the application.

It's a clear indication that students are more interested in mobile applications which supply information arriving in a continuous flow to assist them in their daily work. Although some have mentioned that the display of test results is not important, many see it as an added value to control their academic progress. Indeed, benefits are felt, both to position themselves in relation to the whole class and to stimulate themselves to do better.

Furthermore, the students' responses showed a marked interest in the possibility of being able to modify the graphical interface according to their needs as well as being able to set alerts. These responses corroborate our preliminary study as to the possibility of customising the mobile application according to one's interests and choices. Indeed, personalisation gives the ability to control learning and makes it an active experience in which the learner finds his place.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper proposed to address the essential aspects of m-learning with the use of smartphone as a complement to learning process. M-learning is often defined as a learning method where the learner is not subject to any constraint related to time or space. Then we focus on the access to information at anytime, anywhere and by anyone. Regarding smartphone advantages and limitations, we show what types of services specific to m-learning should be considered as a complement to support learning, especially in computer science.

To achieve this, we developed a mobile application to collect students' views about m-learning as a support. Responding to a survey, the majority of students who used this application expressed their appreciation and the need for an application which provides information arriving in a continuous flow to assist them in their daily work. Furthermore, their responses showed a marked interest in the possibility of being able to modify the graphical interface according to their needs. These responses corroborate our preliminary study as to the possibility of customising the mobile application.

The most immediate scope of future work is to include collaboration aspects which could make the application more interactive and be able to configure and display alarms and deadlines.

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